

Rhenium. Part III.* Thermal Decomposition of Salts of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$

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The thermal decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been studied by thermogravimetry and differential thermal analysis. The chloro compound undergoes decomposition in two stages : $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow [\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $4[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4 + \text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2 + 10\text{py}$. The reaction products have been isolated.

It was observed in a previous communication¹ that dioxotetrapyridinerhenium (V) chloride loses pyridine very slowly, the rate of the loss rapidly increasing with temperature. In case the complex is not completely decomposed, it is likely that chloride which is present in the complex outside the coordination sphere, might enter the coordination zone with the expulsion of pyridine. The mode of the decomposition of the compound with the formation of intermediate products, if any, could suitably be studied by thermogravimetry. Thermogravimetric analysis in combination with differential thermal analysis and chemical analysis of the products is expected to provide an almost unequivocal mechanism of the thermal decomposition. In addition, such studies might also throw some light into the differences that are existent¹ between the various workers regarding the degrees of hydration of the complex. With these objects in view, the thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were undertaken. For comparison the studies have been extended to the corresponding cyanide salt, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared and recrystallised by methods given earlier¹. 117.00 mg. of the air-dried sample of the chloride sieved to pass through mesh size 200 was taken in a quartz bucket and subjected to thermal treatment at a rate of about 5° per min. in a manual thermo-balance, the sensitivity of the balance being 0.05 mg. Heating was continued upto about 600°. In the case of the cyanide compound 110.30 mg. of the air-dried sample sieved to pass through mesh size 200 was similarly treated.

The differential thermal analysis of both the samples was made using manually operated gadgets. Approximately 100 mg. of the air-dried samples (200 mesh) were used in each recording. The heating rate was about 12° per minute.

For isothermal heating known amounts of the substances were placed in a weighing bottle which was heated in an air oven at a constant temperature. At suitable intervals the bottle was cooled in a desiccator for 20 min. and weighed.

* A short communication on this was published in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 654.

1. M. C. Chakravorti, Communicated to this Journal, Part I of this series; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 1043.

The estimation of rhenium, chlorine, nitrogen, carbon and hydrogen in the products was carried out by methods described earlier¹. The determination of the oxidation state of rhenium in the products was carried out by oxidising known amounts of these with weakly alkaline sodium chromate solution by prolonged warming over a water bath. Chromium hydroxide equivalent to the amount of rhenium oxidised to perrhenate was precipitated by boiling the largely diluted solution. In the precipitate chromium was estimated iodometrically. In the filtrate excess of chromate was reduced by sulphur dioxide in presence of HCl and then rhenium separated as Re_2S_7 in which rhenium was estimated by methods given earlier¹.

If v is the volume in ml. of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution consumed in estimation of chromium, and s its strength in normality and w the amount in gm. of rhenium present, then it follows that

$$n = 7 - \frac{186.3 \times v \times s}{1000w}$$

The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using a Perkin-Elmer Infracord (No. 137).

RESULTS

The TGA and DTA plots of the two compounds are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ began to lose weight from 100° . The thermogram showed recognisable stages at about 160° , 210° and 300° . After 550° the weight remained constant and the residue corresponded to about 6.0% of the starting material taken. The residue was not, however, left in the bucket and a volatile substance, presumably Re_2O_7 had condensed on the cooler fibres of the bucket and on the spring. The first weight loss in the TGA curve from 100 – 160° corresponded approximately to 7.0% and probably represents the loss of the two molecules of water, the calculated loss on this basis being 5.9%. The first horizontal corresponding to the formation of anhydrous $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ was not well defined and the loss of water and pyridine took place simultaneously. This has been confirmed by heating a sample of the dihydrate isothermally at 100° when both water and pyridine were lost simultaneously and the loss in weight was about 37.0%. The second rather well defined horizontal extending from 210° to 250° corresponded to the total loss of approximately 38.0%. For investigating the product formed at this stage 0.5 g. of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was isothermally heated at 160° . The pyrolysis curve is shown in Fig. 3. The curve showed an almost constant weight level after the loss was about 38.0%. Thus the same reaction takes place in both isothermal and polythermal heating. From the residue of isothermal heating two substances were isolated in the following way.

The dark green residue left after heating $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 160° was extracted with acetone. The green residue was thoroughly washed with acetone and then dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . The violet acetone solution was slowly evaporated in air to give a violet substance which was then dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 .

Anal. of the green substance. Found : Re, 42.5; Cl, 15.9; N, 6.4; C, 28.0; H, 2.6%; oxidation state of rhenium +4.96. Calcd. for $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$: Re, 42.4; Cl, 16.2; N, 6.4; C, 27.3; H, 2.3%; oxidation state of rhenium +5.

Anal. of the violet substance. Found : Re, 57.6; N, 4.7; C, 18.9; H, 1.8%; oxidation state of rhenium +6.92. Calcd. for $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$: Re, 58.0; N, 4.4; C, 18.7; H, 1.6%; oxidation state of rhenium +7.

The thermal decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ can thus be represented as

The calculated weight loss of the compound on this basis is 38.0%.

Fig. 1—T.G.A. curves of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ complexes

The DTA curve (Fig. 2) of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ showed a very pronounced endothermic peak at 185° followed by a weak exothermic one at 260° . The endothermic peak probably represents the volatilisation of water and also of pyridine to some extent, since the peak occurred approximately at the same temperature as the break in the TGA curve, the slightly higher temperature observed in DTA being due to higher rate of heating. The weak exothermic peak at 260° was probably due to partial oxidation of Re(V) to Re(VII) leading to the formation of $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$. This peak therefore corresponded to the break in TGA curve at 210° . Thus, the thermogravimetry, differential thermal analysis and product analysis collectively point to the following sequence of the thermal decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

At higher temperature the DTA curve showed two more weak endothermic peaks at 290° and 365° and a weak exothermic one at 345° . The peak at 290° which corresponded to the break in TGA at 300° probably represented sublimation and fusion of the mass. The exothermic peak at 345° was probably due to the complete oxidation of Re(V) to Re(VII).

The mode of the decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was generally similar to that of the corresponding chloride. The cyanide began to lose weight from 75° and the loss of water was complete at 150° after which the loss in weight was very rapid until a break at 250° was reached. The horizontal extending from 250 – 310° was not well defined. The two endothermic peaks in the DTA curve (Fig. 2) at 160° and 220° probably represented decomposition and sublimation and the absence of any well defined horizontal in the TGA curve also pointed towards the fact that more than one reaction were taking place simultaneously. This also explains the failure to isolate any pure compound by heating $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 100° , 150° or 200° . After 295° the base was shifted considerably probably because of exothermic changes due to oxidation of carbonaceous matter (possibly cyanide was oxidised to cyanogen, since such pronounced exothermic change was not observed with the chloride).

Fig. 2. D.T.A. curves of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ complexes

Properties of the compounds $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$ and $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$.

The product $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$ obtained by heating $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 160° is dark green. The same substance with a bright green colour is obtained by heating $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at lower temperatures like 100° or 50° . The reaction however, took a much longer period for completion—several weeks when heated at 100° and several months when the temperature was 50° . $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$ is insoluble in water and ethanol and very slightly soluble in acetone. The important bands in IR spectra of the compound were at 1615 vs., 1540 m,

1490 s, 1450 vs, 1400 m, 1360 w, 1240 w, 1220 s, 1155 m, 1070 s, 1050 m, 1015 m, 976 m, 910 vs and 766 (vs) cm^{-1} . The spectrum is thus similar to those of other pyridine complexes studied by Gill *et al.*². The characteristic shift of 1578 (s) cm^{-1} band of pyridine occurs at 1615 (vs) cm^{-1} in this complex. The 976 and 910 cm^{-1} bands are in the region of $\text{Re} = \text{O}$ stretch.

The molecular weight of the substance could not be determined due to its insolubility in solvents. It appears that the substance is identical with the green product obtained by Johnson *et al.*³ by the action of pyridine on a solution of ReCl_5 in acetone.

Fig 3 Isothermal heating curve of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$ is a violet micro crystalline substance insoluble in water and ethanol, but soluble in acetone and nitrobenzene giving pink solutions. It goes into solution in dilute caustic alkali to give a brown solution which on warming turns colourless with the liberation of pyridine and the formation of perrhenate. The IR spectra of the substance gave important bands at 1625 s, 1615 vs, 1530 vs, 1475 vs, 1440 w, 1375 w, 1330 w, 1240 s, 1200 m, 1170 m, 1060 s, 1030 w, 1000 w, 965 w, 745 (br) cm^{-1} . The spectrum is thus similar to that of other pyridine compounds (*vide supra*). The characteristic 1578 (s) cm^{-1} band of pyridine was shifted in this complex also and in fact was resolved into 1625 and 1615 cm^{-1} bands. The 1000 and 965 cm^{-1} bands may be the $\text{Re} = \text{O}$ stretching frequencies. $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$ is probably a polymeric compound involving one or more oxygen bridges.

The mode of the thermal decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ points to the great tendency of pentavalent rhenium compounds towards polymerisation like the pentavalent molybdenum compounds. Thus, instead of giving a simple nonelectrolyte $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_3\text{Cl}]$, the thermal decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ gave two polymeric products $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$ and $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$. A 2,2'-dipyridyl compound of molybdenum, $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3(\text{dipy})_2\text{Cl}_4$, analogous to $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$ has recently been reported by Mitchell⁴.

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